

The role of funding on research quality: the Spanish case

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Introduction

Public investment is one of the primary mechanisms for orienting science, technology, and innovation policies. At the European level, the European Commission recommendations highlight the importance of introducing competitive funding schemes to promote the best researchers, groups, and institutions (ERC, 2023). Competitive allocation is mainly implemented through two different systems: project funding and institutional performance evaluations. In Spain, competitive funding is located almost exclusively through project funding (Zacharewicz et al., 2019) and mainly through the central administration allocates 85% of the public research and innovation project funding and 1,5% is regional funding (AEI, 2022). The Spanish scheme makes central administration project funding the basic financing instrument for research groups to conduct their research activity. This research in progress explores the impact of the projects funded by the ‘National Plan for Scientific and Technical R&I’ (SNP hereafter) from 2013 to 2019, which is the main public research funding provided by the Spanish government –412M€ budget in the 2020 call– and an essential vehicle to consolidate research groups and researchers.

The main aim of this work is to study the influence of funding on the quality of the research carried out by Spanish institutions. Quality is measured as the impact of the publications financed in terms of cites per paper and the presence of articles within the 1% most cited papers worldwide, the greatest visibility in first quartile journals, international collaboration, and open access. We analyze the SNP as the most important and competitive national funding instrument and include research groups from all research areas, institution types and geographical regions.

Methods and Data

We retrieved information from 22,964 SNP-funded projects from 2013 to 2020 (2270M euros in total). We accessed the PDFs of the final resolutions of the SNP Programs ‘Knowledge Generation’ and ‘Societal Challenges’ from 2013 to 2019 from the Spanish National Research Agency’s website –we did not include grants after 2019 for this analysis as there is a time window from the reception of the grant to the first publication, and consequent citations.

For articles data, we first downloaded all articles related to an SNP project from the Web of Science (WoS) using the grant number on the acknowledgment field of the WoS (105,067 articles). Then, articles published in the same period with no funding were retrieved from WoS (355,749 articles). It was assumed that no funding had been procured if the field was empty. The two datasets were merged, and the presence or absence of funding was coded as a dummy variable.

We use descriptive statistics, the Mann-Whitney test, and the z-test to analyze the differences between the two groups regarding average citation counts per paper. For international collaboration, Q1, and open access, we use a two-proportion z-test.

Finally, we use negative binomial regression analysis to explore the relationships between variables further. We used negative binomial regression as our response is an overdispersed count variable. We use citation count from WoS as our response variable to address the impact of academic articles in three models.

Results

Descriptive statistics show that SNP-funded publications outperform non-funded publications in all measures. The differences between SNP-funded and non-funded publications are determined significant by an unpaired Mann-Whitney Test –for citation counts– and two-proportions z-test

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	SNP funded pubs	Non-funded pubs
Avg. Cites/paper	13.3	5.09
Papers in top 1%	1.03%	0.31%
Int. collab.	52.7%	27.9%
Q1	51.86%	41.38%
OA	63.6%	32.8%

For the regression analysis, Model (1) and Model (2) show that funding has significant effects on the citation count, also when research area and publication year are added as controls. Model (3) shows that all variables have positive coefficients but different effects’ intensity. Funding remains the predictor with stronger effects. The model also shows the positive and significant effects of Q1, international collaboration, open access, and author

number in citation counts. The research area and publication year are included as controls.

Table 2. Regression analysis

	<i>Dependent variable</i>		
	<i>Citation count</i>		
	<i>Model(1)</i>	<i>Model(2)</i>	<i>Model(3)</i>
Funding	0.961***	0.946***	0.897***
	(0.007)	(0.008)	(0.007)
Int. collab. (dummy)			0.585***
			(0.006)
Q1 (dummy)			0.719***
			(0.006)
OA (dummy)			0.473***
			(0.006)
Num. authors			0.007***
			(0.0001)
RA controls	No	Yes	Yes
Year controls	No	Yes	Yes
Constant	1.63***	420.92***	464.86***
	(0.003)	(2.564)	(2.465)
Observations	460,843	460,843	460,843
Log Likelihood	-1,178,001	-1,144,344	-1,121,957
theta	0.268***	0.324***	0.371***
	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)
Akaike Inf. Crit.	2,356,005	2,288,702	2,243,936
Note:	* p ** p *** p<0.01		

Discussion and Conclusions

Overall, the results show that funding significantly affects research impact and emphasizes the importance of public investment in scientific projects. However, further research is needed to address the nature of this relationship. Although we find that public funding produces higher quality research -ex-post hypothesis-, as proved earlier (Corsini & Pezzoni, 2022; Beaudry & Allaoui, 2012), it might be the case that funding is allocated to more consolidated and ‘excellent’ groups, so the researchers’ recognition can also play an important role -ex-ante hypothesis- (Bol et al., 2018). Future research may focus on longitudinal studies such as the career trajectory of research groups in order to unveil these relationships. Finally, the results presented here have one main limitation: the inclusion of only one funding instrument. We selected the SNP because it is allocated to all research areas, regions, and institutions, providing a broad overview of Spanish public funding and research outcomes. However, it might be beneficial to include other types of funding, such as regional projects or private funds, to better address the effects of funding and the role of the SNP within the Spanish landscape.

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